

Utilization as target on SDSC-SP2 trace

a) SJF

b) F1

The performance of SchedInspector where the objective is utilization and the trace is SDSC-SP2. y-axis on the right three charts are utilization, average bsld (absld) and maximal bsld (mbsld).